

Management of Fuel Oil in Preserving Indonesian Marine Sovereignty

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Abstract: *Indonesia has a strategic maritime area and is potentially helpful as capital in national development. Indonesia's seas strategic position and potential have many threats that interfere with Indonesia's defense. For this reason, an Indonesian marine defense system form places the Indonesian Navy in the function of defense at sea that upholds Indonesia's sovereignty at sea. In carrying out this task, the Indonesian Navy needs Indonesian Navy ships as an adequate defense system in maintaining naval defenses in Indonesia. In operating the Indonesian navy ships, logistical support for fuel oil is the primary raw material to run Indonesian naval vessels. If the management of fuel oil hampers, it will affect the ability of military operations at sea. This study aims to analyze the logistics management of fuel oil in maintaining Indonesian marine sovereignty. This study uses a qualitative method. The results showed that the Indonesian Navy carried out fuel oil management to support Indonesian marine sovereignty using six stages: fuel demand planning, supply, distribution, use and responsibility, administration, and removal.*

Keywords: fuel oil, Indonesia, management, marine sovereignty

I. INTRODUCTION

Indonesia has a strategic sea route because it locates between two continents, Asia and Australia, and between two oceans, the Indian Ocean and the Pacific Ocean. Indonesia's strategic location provides an advantage because it is a crossing point for sea traffic lanes that connect world trade routes. In addition to its strategic geographical location, Indonesia's marine area also has excellent natural resources, such as fishery potential, to oil and gas. Therefore, Indonesian seas must be protected and defended from damage and illegal actions that can harm the state (Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 32 of 2014 concerning the Sea).

Indonesia's seas strategic position and potential have various threats that interfere with Indonesia's defense. These threats are in the form of transnational crimes in narcotics, people smuggling, weapons smuggling, piracy at sea, theft of natural resources, and separatism (Ministry of Defense, 2015). Since 2021, the Ministry of Maritime Affairs and Fisheries has arrested 82 vessels carrying out illegal fishing activities in the North Natuna Sea, only one part of the vast Indonesian ocean. Based on the analysis of the Indonesian Ocean Justice Initiative (IOJI) using satellite imagery, it knows that illegal fishing activities have been carried out since February 2021 and increased in April 2021. The weak supervision of this unlawful practice is due to the limited ability of ships to protect the sea in Natuna. This causes the Natuna marine area to have a low maritime security level (Ramadhan, 2021).

The government established a marine defense system organized by the Indonesian Ministry of Defense and the Indonesian Navy to defend the sea area from threats and disturbances. The Indonesian Navy duties of the Indonesian National Army in the field of defense is (1) enforce the law and maintain security in the marine area of national jurisdiction by the provisions of national law and ratified international law; (2) carries out the tasks of naval diplomacy to support foreign policy policies set by the government; (3) carry out the duties of the Indonesian National Army in the development and development of the strength of the marine dimension; (4) as well as carry out the empowerment of the marine defense area (Law Number 34 of 2004 concerning the Indonesian National Army).

In dealing with various threats in the sea area, the Indonesian Navy operates the Indonesia warship. The implementation of operations by the Indonesian Navy will not be without logistics that support the task of the operation. One of the logistics that have the most role in operations is fuel oil. A planned, integrated, and sustainable management system is needed to optimize the need for fuel oil in the Navy. The importance of fuel for Indonesia's warship operations is to strengthen the main task of the Indonesian Navy in operations to support defense and sovereignty in the sea area. If the Indonesia warship lacks fuel, the operation will not be optimal. The shortage of fuel oil occurred in 2014 because the supply was limited to security operations in the sea area. In 2014, one ship could only twice

a week in security operations. As a result, the number of state losses due to illegal fishing in 2014 reached IDR 30 trillion. The extent of the territorial waters is not comparable to the Indonesian warship tasked with maritime security patrols. This was exacerbated by the minimal supply of fuel oil in 2014, which was only 32% of the total needs of ships (Silalahi, 2014).

The problem of fuel shortages in 2014 can be used as part of the history of fuel management that is less than optimal and becomes a lesson also basis for the argument that to optimally the fuel needs of the Indonesian Navy. This is also the reason to optimize the fuel for the operation of Indonesian Navy warships. Henry Baron Jomini expressed the importance of internal logistics for the military. He said that "Logistics does not win the battle, but without logistics, the battle will not win." So it is hoped that fuel logistics management can support maximum sea operations to achieve sovereignty at sea.

II. METHODOLOGY

This study uses a qualitative research method with a descriptive approach. According to Sugiyono (2015), qualitative research is a research method based on the philosophy of postpositivist used to examine the condition of natural objects. The researcher is the key instrument, data collection techniques are triangulation, data analysis is inductive or qualitative, and qualitative research results emphasize meaning rather than generalization.

Qualitative descriptive research aims to describe and describe existing phenomena, both natural and human-engineered, which pays more attention to the characteristics, quality, and interrelationships between activities. In addition, descriptive research does not provide treatment, manipulation, or changes to the variables studied but described a condition as it is. The only remedy was the research itself through observation, interviews, and documentation (Sukmadinata, 2011).

Based on the information from several experts above, descriptive qualitative research is a series of activities to obtain data as it is without being under certain conditions, the results of which emphasize meaning. The researcher uses a qualitative descriptive research method to describe how fuel oil logistics management can support operational tasks and strengthen sovereignty in the Indonesian seas.

III. LITERRATURE REVIEW

Logistics Management

Benjamin S. Blanchard's (2005) opinion regarding logistics from a military point of view states that logistics orientation on systems or products includes elements in logistics management. Such as maintenance plans, personnel, supplies support, equipment support, technical data, training and facilities, resource support, computer power, packaging/ packaging facilities, handling, storage, transportation, reliability, and maintainability.

According to the Institute for Defense Analysis (2016), Defense Logistics is a valuable system for managing and delivering all non-human capabilities. Defense logistics consider creating, equipping, sustain and monitoring militaries on the ground to meet operational demands within size and composition constraints. Logistics planning considerations occur at several levels at the national strategic level. Senior leaders do this regarding the strategy, field, focus, and program targeted in logistics management. Second is capability planning, which identifies the logistical capacity needed by the military to support the national strategy. Third, programming is part of allocating planned resources over time to create future forces with the desired capabilities to support operations. Fourth, logistics is the stage to monitor the implementation of the logistics plans and programs while keeping the flow during the process.

According to Ronald H. Ballou (1992), logistics management is a way to plan, implement, and control raw materials, inventories in process, and finished goods to be delivered to customers effectively and efficiently. Meanwhile, according to Siahaya (2012), logistics management is part of supply chain management. So that in the process, the planning, implementation, and control of the flow of goods are carried out effectively and efficiently, including transportation, storage, distribution and services, and related information starting from the place of origin of the goods, to the point of consumption to meet customer needs.

Fuel Oil

Fuel oil is part of the logistics to support the operational tasks by the Indonesian Navy. Therefore, fuel is included in logistical support for the Indonesian Navy. Fuel defines by the Regulation of the Minister of Defense of the Republic of Indonesia Number 5 of 2020 as petroleum obtained from direct management of primary materials or products mixed with chemicals. Fuel oil gets from petroleum (Petroleum) management such as Pertamina/Pertamax Turbo 98, Premium, Avtur (Aviation Turbine Fuel), (Avgas Aviation Gasoline), HSD (High-Speed Diesel/ Gas Oil), Solar Dex, MDF (Marine Diesel) Fuel), Kerosine, fuel oil/MFO (Marine Fuel Oil) and water-methanol (Methanol Mixture) (Minister of Defense Regulation Number 5 of 2020).

Basic Principles Fuel management must meet six principles: the right type, the right quality, the right amount, the right time, the right place, and the proper use. The right type fulfills fuel needs according to its designation, according to the Certificate of Original (COO) or equivalent, and adequate quality. The right amount fulfills fuel needs according to the amount of support. The right time is the fulfillment of fuel needs on time. According to the address, the right place is the fulfillment of fuel needs. The fuel is a class 3 stock material intended to support the operational tasks carried out by the Indonesian Navy. Fuel use classifies for vehicles, stationary engines, sustaining aids, ships, aircraft, and other equipment. Fuel management consists of six implementation functions, fuel demand planning, supply, distribution, use and responsibility, administration, and removal (Minister of Defense Regulation No. 5 of 2020).

The Sovereignty of The Sea

National defense is efforts to defend the sovereignty of the state, the territorial integrity of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia, and the safety of the entire nation from threats and disturbances to the integrity of the nation and state. Sovereignty itself has the meaning of an exclusive right to control an area of government, society, or over oneself. The sovereignty of the Indonesian sea is all efforts made by Indonesia in maintaining territorial integrity, the nation's safety from various threats and disturbances that exist in the sea and have the potential to damage the integrity of the nation and state. The Indonesian sovereignty of the sea can be achieved through national defense efforts, which are part of the function of the state government in achieving national goals. Indonesia's national goals are stated in the 1945 Constitution paragraph 4: to protect the entire nation and the entire homeland of Indonesia, promote public welfare, educate the nation's life, and participate in implementing world order based on independence, eternal peace, and social justice (1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia).

According to the U.S. Naval War College Digital Commons (1991) concept of sea defense was introduced by Julian S Corbett in 1988 as a concept related to maritime strategy to achieve victory at sea. This relates to naval tactics regarding the execution of plans and maneuvers of the naval fleet in battle. The power of sea operations is part of a command, control, and domination so that a country is said to have a navy that is equivalent to air superiority. Military operations carried out by the Indonesian Military began to be divided into military operations for war and military operations other than war. Military operations at sea consist of several operations: destruction operations, amphibious operations, base defense operations, maritime intelligence operations, seaborne military operations, operations to disrupt opposing lines of communication, and operations to protect their lines of communication. Meanwhile, other than war, military operations are carried out for Indonesia's maritime security, such as naval security patrol operations.

IV. DISCUSSION

The implementation of fuel oil management to maintain Indonesia's maritime sovereignty regulate in the Regulation of the Minister of Defense of the Republic of Indonesia Number 5 of 2020. Fuel oil management consists of six logistics management functions: fuel demand planning, supply, distribution, use and responsibility, administration, and removal.

a. Fuel Demand Planning

Fuel management begins with planning each work unit's operational and routine needs based on activity plans and budgets from the previous year. The upper unit prepares activity plans and budgets related to operational plans, strength development, and use of force for land, sea, and air elements within the Indonesian Navy. This is conveyed in stages, starting from the Navy to the Ministry of Defense and Finance. After that, the Ministry of Finance will set a budget implementation list as a reference for using the fuel budget for one fiscal year (Department of Naval Supplies, 2020).

The fuel demand plan is proposed in stages starting from level 3 fuel consumption unit (first-class naval base), level 2 fuel consumption unit (fleet command), and level 1 fuel consumption unit (Department of Naval Supply). Meanwhile, at the user level (Indonesian warships) will request by submitting an Order To Receive (OTR) to the level unit that oversees the ship. The Department of Naval Supplies offers a plan for fuel requirements in quantum/volume form from level 3 units to level 1 units in stages. Furthermore, the need plan submitted by the Head of Naval Operations is a fuel budget requirement plan to the Indonesian army headquarters and the Ministry of Defense. Submission of the budget needs plan through the annual needs plan is adjusted by submitting needs every three months. The need plan submitted by the Department of Naval Supplies, submitted by the Head of Naval Operations to the Minister of Defense, in this case, the Director-General of Defense Planning, the Ministry of Defense, with copies to the TNI Commander and Director-General of the Defense Forces (Minister of Defense Regulation No. 5 of 2020).

b. Fuel Supply

After the demand plan is submitted and approved as a budget, the Department of Naval Supplies will procure fuel previously handled by the Ministry of Defense and the TNI Commander. Fuel oil procurement carries out with fuel oil service providers that are PT Pertamina (Persero) and other business entities, tailored to the needs of the unit level and users. The service provider and the Minister of Defense make a memorandum of understanding whose contents must contain the intent and purpose of the preparation, scope, implementation, validity period of the memorandum of understanding, statements, and guarantees. The memorandum of understanding for fuel procurement must be signed by the Minister of Defense or represented by the Director-General of the Defense Forces of the Ministry of Defense and the President Director of the fuel service provider. The Memorandum of Understanding signed by the Minister of Defense and the President Director of the fuel oil service provider is submitted to each operating unit to make a Cooperation Agreement for the procurement of fuel oil.

The Navy's fuel oil procurement carries out by the Naval Supply Department through a Cooperation Agreement between the Head of Naval Operations represented by the Commitment Making Officer and PT Pertamina (Persero). Cooperation agreements with fuel oil service providers once a year after the budget is approved. In addition to entering into a Cooperation Agreement with PT Pertamina (Persero), the Commitment Making Officer also cooperates with other business entities tailored to the needs of Indonesian warships in the lubricant sector. This happened because not all Indonesian warships used the same lubricant, so they had to purchase from other business entities at the request of the Indonesian warships (Minister of Defense Regulation No. 5 of 2020).

c. fuel distribution

The fuel distribution process is carried out in three stages: handover, distribution, and storage. The distribution of fuel begins with the handover process by issuing the allocation letter documents, fuel distribution orders, and fuel collection orders. Allocation letters divide into three types: (1) Allocation letters issued by the Indonesian National Armed Forces Headquarters; (2) Allocation letters issued by organizational units of each force through their Logistics Assistant; (3) Allocation letters issued by the Ministry of Defense through the Secretariat General. The fuel handover process in the Indonesian Navy is carried out by a logistical assistant and forwarded to the Naval Supplies Service by issuing a letter which is the basis for making a fuel distribution order to level 2 units (Fleet Command). Then the level 2 unit (Fleet Command) will issue a Fuel Retrieval Execution Order for the level 3 unit (first-class naval base).

At the level 2 unit (Fleet Command), the handover process carries out by a fuel service provider approved by the Indonesian National Army Headquarters and the Ministry of Defense, PT Pertamina Persero. The task of the Fleet Command is to distribute fuel to Indonesian warships in its area of responsibility. The distribution of fuel carries out to distribute warships to Indonesia. The distribution begins with Indonesian warships requesting fuel from level 3 units (first-class naval bases). Then the Fleet Command issued an Execution Order for taking fuel to level 3 units to request fuel loading from the nearest PT Pertamina (Persero) from a naval base or warship in need. After PT Pertamina (Persero) received the letter, PT Pertamina (Persero) made a Loading Order submitted to the level 3 unit as evidence and issued a Bunker Receipt for ship loading (Minister of Defense Regulation No. 5 of 2020).

Distribution using transportation equipment prepared by PT Pertamina (Persero), ships or tankers, stockpiling tanks/drums, and General Fuel Filling Stations appointed by PT Pertamina (Persero). Refueling is done on certain days, usually twice a week. The fuel distribution system at the Fleet Command carries out by the Fleet Command and Supplies Service by issuing a Fuel Retrieval Order and determining which Indonesian warships get refueled first depending on the priority scale. The Material and Supply Service Fleet Command letter will be sent to the first-class naval base under the Fleet Command for further loading to Pertamina. Pertamina will send fuel using barges, pipelines located at the naval base, or PT Pertamina (Persero)'s refueling car, which adjusts to the refueling location and conditions of the naval base.

Fuel storage carries out after receiving it from the fuel service provider by placing the fuel into a special tank according to the standards set by the fuel service provider. However, the Naval Supply Service has never stored fuel except for lubricants not from PT Pertamina (Persero). The cooperation between the Ministry of Defense and the TNI with PT Pertamina (Persero) facilitates the distribution of BBM by the Naval Supplies Service to units level 2 (Fleet Command) and level 3 (first-class naval base). The fuel and lubricants supplied from PT Pertamina (Persero) are stored in tanks and warehouses owned by service providers. As for special oils, lubricants other than PT Pertamina (Persero) are stored in the Depot of the Navy Debriefing Center.

Lubricant storage begins with checking by the Warehouse Head. The head of the warehouse will physically inspect the lubricant, the amount and match it with travel documents and documents according to administrative instructions. After the lubricant enters the warehouse, it will record by the Warehouse Head. The Commission Division will re-examine the items warranted by the Department of Naval Supplies before depositing. Then when the goods have been

inspected, the Commission will make an official report, after which the Naval Supplies Center Depot issues an Order for Receiving Goods. After the receipt is made, an invoice is submitted to the Head Depot Debriefing Center to be signed, and it knows that the receipt of the goods is complete. The Head of the Central Procurement Depot will forward the document to the Department of Naval Supplies (Minister of Defense Regulation No. 5 of 2020).

d. Fuel Use and Responsibility

The use of fuel in the Navy and operations at sea is also used for maintenance activities, the intensity of preparedness movements, operational tasks and training, routine activities, and other activities requiring fuel. While accountability is generally carried out in stages, starting from Indonesian warships to level 3 units (first-class naval bases), then to level 2 units (Fleet Command), and up to level 1 units (Department of Naval Supplies). The results of the accountability at the Department of Naval Supplies are reports to the Logistics Assistant to forwards to the Head of Naval Operations, the Inspectorate General of the Navy, the Director-General of Defense Forces of the Ministry of Defense, and the Director-General of Defense Planning of the Ministry of Defense.

The Fleet Command Logistics Assistant controls the use and accountability of level 2 units (Fleet Command). The Head of Sub Inventory of Materials and Supplies Services for the Fleet Command is in control and distribution. The Head of Sub-Inventory brings a daily fuel usage report to the logistics staff to submit to the Fleet Command Logistics Assistant. The report is via the smartphone application that is Whatsapp. Ships carrying out operations will send reports via Telegram to report the condition of Liquid Logistics, including fuel conditions. The report will submit by Indonesian warships, which operate every 06.00 and 18.00. This report was made for level 3 units (first-class naval base) and level 2 units (Fleet Command). However, the weekly report, by sending a letter regarding the Weekly Material Report, in the letter also explains the condition of fuel oil every week. However, every week only reports on fuel oil, lubricants, and water (Minister of Defense Regulation No. 5 of 2020).

e. Fuel Administration

The implementation of the fuel oil administration adjusts to the Regulation of the Minister of Defense. Administration consists of three activities, namely fuel bookkeeping, fuel recording, and fuel inventory/data collection. At unit level 1 (Department of Naval Supplies), the bookkeeping and recording of fuel is included in the inventory application of State-Owned Enterprises. The records contain beginning fuel inventory, fuel receipts, fuel expenditures, fuel write-offs, and residual fuel inventories. The recording of fuel oil in the inventory application carries out at the Naval Supply Department by recording it first with the purchase transaction. The first recording follows the fuel allocation letter per quarter with the amount/quantum and value/price stated on the allocation letter. Then the Naval Supplies Service makes an outgoing transfer transaction with the amount/quantum and price value listed on the Fuel Distribution Order, submitted to the level 2 unit (Fleet Command).

Fleet Command conducts the following administrative processes by conducting incoming transfer transactions with the amount/quantum and value/price listed on the Material Distribution Order and issuing a Fuel Retrieval Order Execution Letter for level 3 units (first-class naval base). The Navy Base carries out a physical collection of fuel oil to the fuel service provider (PT Pertamina Persero) to further record incoming transfer transactions with the amount/quantum and value/price stated in the letter, not using the original value of the purchase. Next, the level 3 units dispense fuel by inventory exit or usage transactions to the user units.

After levels 1, 2, and 3 units have been distributed, the Naval Supply Department, as the level 1 unit, fills out and sends data in the Management Information System Application and State Property Accounting which contains data or history of recording fuel every month into the accounting system finance. Matching and research carried out on the fuel used. Matching and research prevent differences in price values between inventory applications and the results of matching and analysis, including the financial accounting system. Suppose there was a difference in the system and reports, the settlement adjusting journal in the financial accounting system. The naval base supply service unit's inventory/data collection system carries out through the implementation of stock-taking at least once a semester (Department of Naval Supplies, 2020).

The Fleet Command's Materials and Supplies Department, as a level 2 unit, only records letters that have been issued for use. Indonesian warships that carry out recording and bookkeeping. There are plans to use a computer system for recording BBM, and the application is currently being refined by the Ministry of Defense and the Indonesian National Armed Forces Headquarters. The application is called e-BMP, which stands for fuel electronics. Its application has been socialized to the Indonesian Navy Headquarters, and the application will simplify the fuel inventory and recording system so that the data entered will be more transparent (Priyono, 2020).

f. Fuel Removal

The removal of fuel is rare in the Indonesian Navy. It is because fuel is a logistics that runs out quickly, so there is no need to delete it. However, elimination can occur if the fuel is damaged or contaminated, uneconomical and unusable, and shrinks. The elimination process must guide by regulations fuel elimination, which is also related to the management of state property. Every fuel in the Indonesian Navy includes in the application for recording state goods. Suppose the fuel removal mechanism has to implement. In that case, the first stage is a report from the user or Indonesia warship to the level 3 unit (first-class naval base) regarding the fuel onboard for a lab test regarding its suitability for use. The removal of fuel stored at the Depot of the Supply Center has the same procedure, which is to report to the unit level above it, in this case, the Naval Supply Department for fuel lab tests. The test results stating the unworthiness will be subject to criticism. The censure process begins with reporting the fuel that needs to be criticized. Then, a team of censure commission was formed, which would also conduct research on the quality of fuel based on the laboratory tests carried out. The fuel quality inspection report will be used to reference whether the fuel is eligible to be abolished or not. The report is followed by the process of publishing the Minutes of Disapproval.

Suppose the results of the fuel laboratory test are eligible to be abolished. In that case, the Naval Supply Department will report the proposal for elimination and form an Elimination Commission Team. Then the Naval Supply Department will submit to the commander of the Indonesian National Army to issue a letter of recommendation for deletion and a Minutes of Elimination. Based on a request for abolition from the commander of the Indonesian National Army to the Minister of Defense. The Minister of Defense applies for approval to proposal abolition to the Minister of Finance as part of the management of state goods. Based on the support of the dissolution of fuel products from the Minister of Finance, the Minister of Defense issues an Elimination Decree, which is then forwarded to the central command bases to issue an Elimination Order. Then the Head of the level unit carries out the removal according to the procedure. Fuel removed from inventory is documentation, administrative data, and biological data. The fuel removed from the Indonesia warship will be accommodated in a level 3 unit (first-class naval base). The foreign service will contact it for the destruction process by the first-class naval base. Likewise, the fuel stored at the Depot for the Debriefing Center will accommodate the Depo at the Debriefing Center before being sent via a transporter appointed by the Naval Supply Department from the Foreign Service. According to the procedure, the outside service will destroy it and not pollute the environment (Minister of Defense Regulation No. 5 of 2020).

V. CONCLUSIONS

The implementation of fuel oil management for Indonesia's maritime sovereignty needs to regulate in the Regulation of the Minister of Defense of the Republic of Indonesia Number 5 of 2020 concerning Fuel Oil and Lubricants. Fuel Oil and Lubricants Management consists of six logistics management functions: making demand plans, procuring, distributing, using, and accounting for, administering, and writing off books. The management of BBM in the Navy has been carried out correctly to support the operational tasks of the Navy effectively and efficiently and realize state sovereignty at sea.

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